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The Definition, Development, and Defense of Political Fantasy

Emily C. A. Snyder

Introduction (2000)

The following paper is my Senior English thesis for the Franciscan University of Steubenville, my alma mater. However, since I have written this paper (and, more importantly, since I have recovered from voluntary sleep-deprivation á la excessive amounts of caffeine which were required to *finish* this paper), I have realized that what I had *hoped* was merely a 20-some-odd blow-off, actually wants to be something rather longer.

Thus, you will no doubt note that during the course of this paper, there are sections that tentatively push into another area that hopes to one day be a chapter in its own right. You will notice blatant holes in my argument, which I will blame on aforementioned sleep-deprivation. You will notice a rather inconclusive ending (which I blame on the silly deadline of graduation - yeesh!) And, if you're anything as nitpicky as I am, you will wonder, 'Why doesn't this chiqua get her act together and cover every bit of the arts since this paper is *clearly* determined to be something larger than 20 pages!'

The answer is: I'm working on it. In the nonce, however, you will have to content yourself that someday, far far in the future, there *will* be a 20 *VOLUME* set all about "Defining the Arts" (but with a title appropriately larger and more cumbersome, including several neat-o uses of the colon and font type)...or at least a longer treatise.

In short, what you are reading is not a finished product by any stretch of the imagination, but it is more or less a sort of extended outline. When I get the chance, I'll post a second essay which attempts to deal solely with the Hierarchy of the Arts.

Because of browser constraints, the paper is divided in parts, with all appendices on their own pages. These pages are therefore always "under construction." I welcome any and all suggestions, questions and arguments concerning this paper/outline, but warn you that I check my e-mail not quite as frequently as some.

Thesis (1999)

Definition

Political Fantasy is the study of politics (the force-human or divine-that moves and shapes a society) in a fabricated world. In the literary hierarchy, it exists as an unrecognized subgenre, often hiding behind the usual terms of high or traditional or speculative fantasy. But Political Fantasy, like Political Fiction of all types, is unique in the possible impact it can have on the world, for it touches the very force behind society, and thus can be a means of political change as well. Unfortunately, Political Fantasy as such does not yet formally exist. But with numerous subgenres coming into existence yearly, the advent of Political Fantasy cannot be long delayed.

In an age where words have been redefined so that the usage prescribed in a dictionary does not necessarily match what the common mind normally ascribes to that same jumble of vowels and consonants, a brief explanation of the words used here is required. (See also Glossary.) In this case, we consider "Literature," the FORM, to be divided into various STYLES, such as "Poetry," "Plays" and "Prose." The latter category is divided into two CLASSIFICATIONS, "Fiction" and "Non-fiction." These classifications are then divided into the SUPERGENRES, such as "Realistic Fiction" and "Fantastic Fiction" under the classification "Fiction." These SUPERGENRES may then divided, in the case of the latter, into "Science Fiction," "Fantasy," and any other literature that has elements of the fantastic. "Fantasy," a GENRE, is then divided into "Dark Fantasy," "High Fantasy," "Steampunk," et cetera, and other SUBGENRES, including "Political Fantasy."

"Literature" pertains to books, magazines, articles, plays, short stories, poems-anything that utilizes the written word. "Prose" is the organization of the written word into paragraph form. The difference between "Fiction" and "Non-fiction" is that the former is based on something that did not happen or has not happened, and the latter is consequently based on something that has happened or is happening. So both a fiction and a nonfiction book may be set in World War II, but the first will fabricate nonexistent characters, while the second will be constrained to report who actually was there. "Realistic fiction" is any fiction that takes place within the confines of this world, with little to no aberration in its present history, physics or dynamics. "Fantastic Fiction" is any fiction that takes place within the confines of another world, or in this world but with significant aberration within its history, future, physics or dynamics. The two largest Genres within Fantastic Fiction are "Science Fiction" and "Fantasy." The common words "Science Fiction" and "Fantasy" are used here in the accepted sense they have come to acquire in the commercial world. Although this paper defines these words more specifically, as well as adding in their terms to further clarify the modern hodge-podge that we call "literature," I have deemed it best to implement working terms regardless of their etymological roots.

Often mistakenly lumped together, these two genres are better explained distinctly. Fantasy is the purest form of Fantastic Fiction: the majority of the action does not take place within this world. “Magic” is not a necessity for the fantasy genre—the creation of a completely foreign world is. Therefore “Fantasy” may encompass those books previously considered to be “Science Fiction” wherein another world is created outside of the existing one, with elements of advanced scientific development. Currently, this genre is sometimes known as “Science Fantasy.” As for the use of “magic:” this is merely a traditional literary device in “Fantasy,” previously thought of as a necessity to “qualify” in the genre, but actually useful only as a means of differentiating another world from our own. Fantastic fiction will almost certainly include those books that incorporate “magic” or any other paranormal event, whether set in this world or another, except in those cases where the “magic” (in our world) is not a literary device (and purely fantastic and impossible), but frighteningly true. There are supernatural forces in the world, and those sources have been defined and revealed by such reliable sources as the Holy Bible. Therefore, those books that deal with spiritual phenomena may also be placed under the term “realistic fiction.”

Science Fiction is another form of Fantastic Fiction in which often the majority of the action takes place in a technologically advanced age, usually in the future of this world. For purposes of this paper, the term “Science Fiction” will refer only to those works that remain within the confines of this world and universe but include the fantastic element of incredible scientific development. The creation of a completely different world belongs solely to “Fantasy,” regardless of what technological advances are or are not explored in the work.

The use of the word “world” here refers to what is described in Genesis 1-2, or, in literature, any variation on what God has done (with the realization that all we “create” is due solely to what God has truly Created). A fabricated world may then be a place where the structure is changed so that all the characters live in clouds, or the water is orange, or five suns circle the planet—yet these fabrications are the rearrangements of elements found in this true world. A world, often used in parallel universe stories, that has similar dynamics to this one (trees are green, humans are prevalent, etc.) may still be considered fabricated if the sociopolitical structure is different (e.g., a world where Hitler won, a world where words have been stripped of meaning, etc.). In short, the particulars of a given world are all that differentiate “worlds” from one another. A story set in the future of this world is not considered a different world but speculative, since the basics of God’s creation necessarily remain intact.

In any world, however, one crucial element must be observed in order to make the fantastic plausible: the characters must be human, or humanlike. As G.K. Chesterton wrote in *Orthodoxy*:

This is also why the new novels die so quickly, and why the old fairy tales endure for ever. The old fairy tale makes the hero a normal human boy; it is his adventures that are startling; they startle him because he is normal. But in the modern psychological novel the hero is abnormal; the centre is not central.¹

Political Fantasy, then, is a subgenre of Fantasy, differentiated from Political Science Fiction by its being a completely different world rather than a speculation on this world. The emphasis or study of this world, though, centers not merely on the social (i.e., human) interactions, but on the form of politics (or the distribution of power) as it affects society. The emphasis on politics rather

¹ Chesterton, G. K. *Orthodoxy*. San Francisco: Ignatius Press, (c) 1908.

than society merely indicates a sharpening in perspective or study from the social or everyday interactions of a given world to the forces that formed those everyday interactions. Politics is the human force behind a world, so often flawed because it is human rather than divine. But, as some philosophers assert, we are political beings, and the study of that political nature should be a concern for the educated reader.

The purpose and base of Political Fantasy, as with all fantasy and with all fiction, are the ramifications of and the current trends in our present world. In Political Fantasy, however, one sees a certain sociopolitical trend in our world and, by placing it in another world (a sort of literary “vacuum” or “laboratory”), allows that trend to follow through to its extreme logical absurdity. Hence, in *Last Words*, the author saw the movement towards the reduction of the English Lexicon, the political power inherent in such a move, and its devastating effects. Although the society, or world, created in *Last Words* is by no means meant to be prophetic, indicative, or historical, it is meant to be a sort of warning “might.”

More than any other genre, Fantasy has the advantage of not being tied to this world, so that such an experiment in literature will not be seen-cannot be seen-as prophetic, indicative, or historical. In excellent Political Science Fiction books such as *1984*, the reader can wave away the warnings of the novel because the author’s “future” has come and passed without his world coming into being. Similarly, those novels that change our world’s history to achieve an alternate earth in which to set their political warning can be dismissed by their sheer impossibility-history is immutable. Fantasy, however, is “might,” rather than the “should” or “could” that exists in science fiction and alternate history. Although skeptics may still doubt the influence of an impossible and non-existent literary society upon our own reading populace (since the society never happened in any actual dimension), yet fantasy is a sort of parable, a sort of rippled water, that makes us look at situations present in our world today as though they were something uncommon. Fantasy is that funhouse looking glass that makes us view ourselves from angles never before perceived.

Development

Political Fiction is nothing revolutionary. Indeed, there are even historic precedents of it. As always, we look first to the Greeks. Plato’s *Republic*, although a speculative political philosophic work, becomes a springboard for political fantasy’s “what-if” format. Here Plato, speaking through or for Socrates, sets up a communistic society where children are cared for in common, men are assigned positions according to their nature, “Guardians” (the cream of society) of both sexes care for the daily needs of the society, and the whole is ruled by the famous “philosopher king.”

Until philosophers are kings, or the kings and princes of this world have the spirit and power of philosophy, and political greatness and wisdom meet in one...cities will never have rest from their evils-no, nor the human race, as I believe-and then only will this our State have a possibility of life and behold the light of day.²

The main difference between Political Fiction, or Political Fantasy, and this Speculative Political Philosophy, is that while a completely different society is created, qualifying it for fantastic fiction,

² Plato. “The Republic.” *Plato*. Trans. J. Harward. Chicago: Encyclopaedia Britannica, Inc., (c) 1952. p. 369.

the work does not employ the standards of character or plot necessary for prose fiction. Given Plato's ostensible dislike for poetry or any fabrication, one is surprised that he even flirts with the creation of a different society.

Conversely, Homer's *Iliad* is an excellent example of Political Literature whose scope to the modern reader may at first be considered fantastic, comprising as it does the workings of gods, magic, heroes and fate. But the modern reader must remember that this classic work was written in the completely realistic vein of its time and therefore is an example of Political Fiction, although its style and indeed all mythology contributed to the development of modern fantasy.

The Iliad is, in one sense, the story of what happens when political leaders put their own interests before the interests of their people. Beginning with the power struggle between Achilles and Agamemnon over Briseis and then blossoming out to encompass the larger political struggle between the Achaeans and the Trojans over Helen, Homer dissects the politics that begin and sustain a war. "Courage is the secret of power," Diomedes rebukes Agamemnon in the ninth chapter, followed soon after by Nestor's advice that "man is indeed an enemy of his country, clan and hearth who enjoys the bitter taste of civil war."³ Likewise, Priam shows his own kingly weakness when he says to Helen, "I bear you no ill will at all: I blame the gods."⁴

Homer does not stop at the selfish politics of the Greeks and the Trojans, but probes even the hierarchy of the gods, since the divine has a place in every political schema. Zeus is the king of the gods, manipulating his court and their involvement in the war. He proves the classical ideal of an absolute monarchy-as well as its practical impossibility-when he rebukes his nagging (and often successfully political) wife, Hera, by saying, "When I choose to take a step without referring to the gods, you are not to cross-examine me about it."⁵ However, even Zeus is subject to Fate: "Father Zeus hung his golden balances and set in one the lot of Hector's death and in the other that of Achilles. Hector's lot sank down. It was appointed that he should die."⁶

Following fast on the heels of *The Iliad* is Virgil's *Aeneid*. This classic Roman epic's whole scope is consumed by Aeneas' destiny to be the founder of Rome, and from there of the Roman Empire. Again Fate takes a prominent place in the political hierarchy of the ancient world, as the opening stanza proves.

Arms and the man I sing, who, forced by Fate,
And haughty Juno's unrelenting hate,
Expelled and exiled, left the Trojan shore.
Long labors, both by sea and land, he bore,
And in the doubtful war, before he won
The Latian realm, and built the destined town;
His banished gods restored to rites divine:
And settled sure succession in his line,
From whence the race of Alban fathers come,
And the long glories of majestic Rome.⁷

³ Homer. *Iliad*. Trans. E. V. Rieu. Baltimore: Penguin Books, (c) 1966. p. 162.

⁴ Ibid. p. 68.

⁵ Ibid. p. 37.

⁶ Hamilton, Edith. *Mythology: Timeless Tales of Gods and Heroes*. New York: Mentor Books, (c) 1942. p. 190.

⁷ Virgil. *Aeneid*. Trans. John Dryden. New York: Hurst & Company, (c) unknown. p. 11

His first encounter with a royal monarch after the fall of Ilium is with Dido, Queen of Carthage, who again proves the destructive nature of a selfish monarch. As her sister laments over Dido's dead body, "At once thou hast destroyed thyself and me,/Thy town, thy senate, and thy colony!"⁸ Although the gods and destiny compel Æneas to found what was to be the greatest empire of the ancient world, still Æneas must overcome on his own those tender-hearted sentiments so atypical of the ideal Roman citizen. Therefore Virgil ends the epic with the hero's deliberate murder of his last obstacle to Rome. "He rolled his eyes, and every moment felt/His manly soul with more compassion melt;/When, casting down a casual glance, he spied/The golden belt that glittered on his side.../Then, roused anew to wrath.../He raised his arm aloft, and.../Deep in [Turnus'] bosom drove the shining sword."⁹

Shakespeare's histories hone the art of political literature, especially in the creative non-fiction play *Richard III*. While the great epics dealt with several themes, including the political, the master bard's play centers on one man's attempt to win and hold the throne of England by any means necessary. Several deaths are brought about at the usurper's hands, as well as a seduction, and finally a war that disposes of the tyrant. Shakespeare focuses on the question of how such a man could come into power.

England hath long been mad, and scarred herself-
The brother blindly shed the brother's blood,
The father rashly slaughtered his own son,
The son, compelled, been butcher to the sire....
Abate the edge of traitors, gracious Lord,
That would reduce these bloody days again
And make poor England weep in streams of blood!¹⁰

Shakespeare's *Julius Caesar* also questions how easily a society can be reshaped by a political creature. Mark Antony's famous speech in Act III is a classic example of soapboxing. "The noble Brutus/Hath told you Caesar was ambitious./If it were so, it was a grievous fault,/And grievously hath Caesar answered it.../[Caesar] was my friend, faithful and just to me./But Brutus says he was ambitious,/And Brutus is an honorable man."¹¹ By the repetition of this last phrase, Mark Antony is able to turn the tide against Brutus by the use of grim irony. Shakespeare has successfully dissected a political move, laying it bare for those who would see the same manipulation in the politics of his own day. But Shakespeare did not stop there. He also introduced some of the first "realistic" and supposedly "non-fiction" plays that spilled over into the fantastic. *Hamlet*, a laboratory for the destructive nature of revenge in a political situation, includes a ghost whose impetus begins and continues the whole of the action with the words, "Revenge his foul and most unnatural murder."¹² Likewise, *Macbeth* includes the fantastic elements of not only a ghost, but also witches who spur on the action. After first meeting the weird sisters in Act I,

⁸ Ibid. p. 117.

⁹ Ibid. p. 364.

¹⁰ Shakespeare, William. "Richard III." *Shakespeare: The Complete Works*. New York: Harcourt, Brace & World, Inc., (c) 1968. p. 269.

¹¹ Shakespeare, William. "Julius Caesar." *Shakespeare: The Complete Works*. New York: Harcourt, Brace & World, Inc., (c) 1968. p. 832.

¹² Shakespeare, William. "Hamlet." *Shakespeare: The Complete Works*. New York: Harcourt, Brace & World, Inc., (c) 1968. p. 894.

Macbeth says, “My thought, whose murder yet is but fantastical,/Shakes so my single state of man that function/Is smothered in surmise, and nothing is/But what is not.”¹³

The element of the fantastic is continued and expanded on in Saint Thomas More’s *Utopia*. Indeed, except that the country of Utopia could be found somewhere in this world, the classic satire could almost pass for a perfect example of Political Fantasy. In the work, More takes the political and social absurdities and brings them to their logical conclusion in this fictional country in order to make the reader acutely aware of them. In the first book, he condemns certain English practices through the mouth of the sailor Raphael Hythloday, such as the famous line, “In this point, I pray you, what other thing do you, than make thieves and then punish them?”¹⁴ Book two then describes Utopia and its outrageous laws, which all too closely resemble our modern state. The inhabitants preach a religion of “tolerance,” such as Voltaire described in the Enlightenment, decreeing that “no man shall be blamed for reasoning in the maintenance of his own religion.”¹⁵ The result, of course, is Protestantism, or “liberal” Christian theology. Men and women are equalized, working together in the fields and towns, and even going into battle together. All this is decreed by the councils and the king.

More’s *Utopia* still lacks the element of driving plot, rather than plot narration, that is a key element in fiction. The work is somewhere between Plato’s Republic and the modern examples of Political Fantastic Fiction. As if to remedy this, and to carry on and expand More’s remarkable book, Jonathan Swift offers the world *Gulliver’s Travels*. Again written with a keen satiric edge, this book leans more towards the novel form than the treatise. Besides the use of plot and main character, the work explores four different sociopolitical fabricated nations. Because of the time period Swift wrote in, the option of completely separating these created places from this world altogether was not explored, much less known, but the ties to this world are tenuous at best, only found in Gulliver himself.

The three books describe several different nations, each radically different from the others. The first is that of the Lilliputians, who are ruled by an Emperor, extraordinarily small in stature but self-important enough to make up for this apparent deficiency. The second book concerns itself with the nation of Brobdingnag, the home of the peaceful monarchial giants, whose king comments on our society that “I cannot but conclude the bulk of your natives to be the most pernicious race of little odious vermin that nature ever suffered to crawl upon the surface of the earth.”¹⁶

Laputa, the third country, is entirely peopled and governed by “enlightened” intellectuals whose bodies reveal their overweening “rationale.”

Their heads were all reclined either to the right or the left; one of their eyes turned inward, and the other directly up to the zenith.... It seems the minds of these people are so taken up with intense speculations that they can neither speak nor attend to the discourses without being roused by some external taction upon the organs of speech and hearing.¹⁷

¹³ Shakespeare, William. “Macbeth.” *Shakespeare: The Complete Works*. New York: Harcourt, Brace & World, Inc., (c) 1968. p. 1192.

¹⁴ More, Saint Thomas. “Utopia.” *Machiavelli, More, Luther*. Trans. Ralph Robinson. New York: P. F. Collier & Son, (c) 1910. p. 157.

¹⁵ *Ibid.* p. 239.

¹⁶ Swift, Jonathan. *Gulliver’s Travels*. New York: Grosset & Dunlap, (c) 1963. p. 129.

¹⁷ *Ibid.* pp. 157-158.

Combined with Laputa, the floating island, is Lagado, the metropolis beneath it, which is run ragged attempting to keep up with the times. As one noble comments, “he must throw down his houses in town and country, to rebuild them after the present mode...and give the same directions to all his tenants, unless he would submit to incur the censure of pride, singularity, affectation, ignorance, caprice, and perhaps increase his Majesty’s displeasure.”¹⁸ Glubbudubdrib, the land of magicians and especially necromancers, explores this world’s history, concluding with Gulliver’s saying that he was “chiefly disgusted with modern history.... I found how the world had been misled by writers....how many villains had been exalted to high places.”¹⁹ Luggnagg’s king is more totalitarian, as well as sadistic—a feature demonstrated by the poisonous dust that persons in disfavor are required to lick.

The final nation is the Houyhnhnm’s Country—a nation completely governed, not by a philosopher king, an aristocracy, or any sort of human politic—but by horses in a type of community. In this society, Swift studies the use of lying, or as the Houyhnhnms say, “the thing which was not. (For they have no word in their language to express lying or falsehood.)”²⁰ In this particular country, Swift also introduces “Yahoos,” who are Darwinian devolved humans—the only ones capable of deceit. The meaning is clear: only true brutes (humans) can deceive, and use deceit in governing. As Swift says, “Power, government, war, law, punishment, and a thousand other things had no terms wherein his language could express them, which made it difficult to give my master any conception of what I meant.”²¹ From this country only, Gulliver is forced to return home (rather than fleeing back to England). As he explains, “When I thought of...[the] human race in general, I considered them as they really were: Yahoos in shape and disposition, perhaps a little more civilized...but making no other use of reason than to improve and multiply their vices.”²²

Even Swift’s excellent book, though, has not completed the change from Political Fiction to Political Fantasy, and indeed still has remnants of a cleverly hidden political philosophic work. Not until this century has true Fantasy been possible, and in that genre, only a few have dared to touch upon the possibilities inherent in the subgenre of Political Fantasy. Indeed, if the Supergenre of Fantastic Fiction has been utilized for the study of politics in fiction form, Science Fiction has held sway almost exclusively.

Let us briefly return to the definitions and prerequisites for Political Fiction, both Fantastic and Realistic. Fiction necessitates a definite plot, discovered by characters, exemplifying a thought (or idea). This is different from political treatises whose main thrust is the thought-plot and characters become optional secondary devices to make the work palatable, such as Socrates’ dialogues, or More’s *Utopia*. Both Fantastic and Realistic Fiction, then, use plot and character as the necessary primary devices in order to exemplify the thought. For art and media of any kind is a sort of everyman’s philosophy.

This fervor of poesy is sublime in its effects: it impels the soul to a longing for utterance; it brings forth strange and unheard-of creations of the mind; it arranges these meditations in a fixed order, adorns the whole composition with interweaving of words and thoughts; and thus it veils truth in a fair and fitting garment of fiction.²³

¹⁸ Ibid. p. 172.

¹⁹ Ibid. p. 188.

²⁰ Ibid. p. 211.

²¹ Ibid. p. 220.

²² Ibid. p. 235.

²³ Boccaccio, Giovanni. “The Genealogy of the Gentile Gods.” Trans. Charles G. Osgood. *Dramatic Theory and Criticism: Greeks to Grotowski*. Ed. Bernard F. Dukore. Orlando: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich College Publishers, (c) 1974. p. 105.

But Political Fiction is that literary dissection of the moving forces behind a society. The author focuses on one political system and studies it through the means of his craft. Political Science Fiction, then, focuses on a speculative political system in the future of our world, or somewhere in our universe. The result is literary extrapolation of a certain political evident in today's society.

Orwell's *1984* is perhaps the preeminent example of Political Science Fiction. Written around the time of the Second World War, the book examines the methods used by totalitarianism: the manipulation of history, words, and ideas upon the common man. The story follows an everyman, such as Chesterton advises: Winston Smith, who struggles against the mindnumbing world of "Big Brother," and fails. The slogans "War is Peace. Freedom is Slavery. Ignorance is Strength"²⁴ immediately demonstrate the twists that the political regime has set up against common sense. "Newspeak," a regulation of words, is obviously a political move to control the people, as much as the "Two Minutes Hate" and the "Junior Anti-Sex League."

"The A vocabulary consisted of the words needed for the business of everyday life.... It was composed almost entirely of words that we already possess...but in comparison with the present-day English vocabulary, their number was extremely small, while their meanings were far more rigidly defined. All ambiguities and shades of meaning had been purged out of them.... The B vocabulary consisted of words which had been deliberately constructed for political purposes: words, that is to say, which not only had in every case a political implication, but were intended to impose a desirable mental attitude upon the person using them.... The C vocabulary was supplementary to the others and consisted entirely of scientific and technical terms."²⁵

Orwell was not unaware of the import or subject of his work in this particular subgenre. In his essay "Why I Write," he says:

What I have most wanted to do throughout the past ten years is to make political writing into an art. My starting point is always a feeling of partisanship, a sense of injustice.... I write it because there is some lie that I want to expose, some fact to which I want to draw attention, and my initial concern is to get a hearing.²⁶

And a hearing Orwell received. *1984* is read in almost every school, one of the few fantastic fiction books to "get a hearing," to be considered worthy of notice by those smaller political forces that determine the academic curriculum. Another author concerned with the political power of literature is Ray Bradbury, whose *Fahrenheit 451* is as highly revered in the educational system as *1984*. In Bradbury's vision of the future, the "firemen"—of whom the main character, Guy Montag, is one—burn books, rather than putting out fires. Like *1984*, Bradbury is concerned with

²⁴ Orwell, George. "1984." *The Orwell Reader*. New York: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich, Inc., (c) 1956. p. 398.

²⁵ *Ibid.* p. 410, 412, 417.

²⁶ Orwell, George. "Why I Write." *The Orwell Reader*. New York: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich, Inc., (c) 1956. p. 394.

the political move to dehumanize the people, in this case through massive home entertainment cinemas: wall-TV. As Clarisse McClellan, the voice of normality, says, "People don't talk about anything."²⁷ Later, as Montag discovers his burgeoning contempt for a world so full of nothingness, he wonders, "How do you get so empty?...Who takes it out of you?"²⁸ Beatty, the Firechief, answers,

It didn't come from the Government down. There was no dictum, no declaration, no censorship to start with, no! Technology, mass exploitation, and minority pressure carried the trick.... We must all be alike. Not everyone born free and equal, as the Constitution says, but everyone made equal.... A book is a loaded gun in the house next door. Burn it.... Who knows who might be the target of the well-read man?²⁹

Unlike Orwell's dismal view of such a restrictive society, however, Bradbury offers hope at the end of the book. Montag, fleeing from his home, comes upon a group of renegades who store books in their minds, word for word, until they become "nothing more than dust-jackets for books."³⁰ And ultimately, the world Bradbury envisions—a world that burned books and the men who wrote those books—burns itself in the light of a single bomb, leaving behind only those who kept to the old ways. As the book asks,

Is the purpose of a government to make people happy or to make them bigger, deeper individuals even if this does not lead them to happiness?... In any organization, how much difference do you allow under the name of democracy or tolerance before you have to destroy the difference in order to preserve your organization?³¹

Huxley's *Brave New World* is the third of the major Political Science Fiction works, although there are certainly many others within the Genre. Like his contemporaries, Huxley concerns himself with what he and the others see as the main threat inherent in the present politics of the world: the dehumanization factor. In *Brave New World*, Huxley introduces the theme as he sees it: either national or supernational totalitarianism, "developing, under the need for efficiency and stability, into the welfare-tyranny of Utopia."³² Like Orwell and Bradbury, Huxley wrote his masterpiece in the political chaos during and after the Second World War, developing a future similar to the visions of *1984* and *Fahrenheit 451*.

In this society, all children are marked from birth according to their grade value—indeed, they are bred as a certain type of human from the very outset, rather like a scientifically advanced *Republic*. " 'We also predestine and condition. We decant our babies as socialized human beings, as Alphas or Epsilons, as future sewage workers or future....' He was going to say 'future World

²⁷ Bradbury, Ray. *Fahrenheit 451*. New York: Ballantine Books, Inc., (c) 1953. p. 28.

²⁸ Ibid. p. 40.

²⁹ Ibid. p. 53.

³⁰ Ibid. p. 136.

³¹ Tyre, Richard H. "A Note to Teachers and Parents." *Fahrenheit 451*. New York: Ballantine Books, Inc., (c) 1953. p. 1-2.

³² Huxley, Aldous. "Forward." *Brave New World*. New York: Bantam Books, (c) 1960. p. xiv.

controllers.’ ”³³ Proletariats and politicians are formed by those very “World controllers. Huxley from the beginning shows us the dangerous political possibilities man could have over his fellow man if allowed to dabble into that miracle of generation.

The plot is complicated when the world, stupefied by its soma drugs, happens upon a Savage-one who has lived in what we would consider a normal fashion, “at one with the earth.” He is immediately set upon, studied, and eventually brought out of all society and into a final confrontation with the Controller himself. In that interview, they discuss several issues pertinent to the question of who holds the reins of politics: man, society, or God. As the Controller says of his society, “People believe in God because they’ve been conditioned to believe in God.... But [God’s] code of law is dictated, in the last resort, by the people who organize society; Providence takes its cue from men.”³⁴

With this simple interchange, Huxley touches on the quivering heartbeat of the true struggle of politics through the ages: the struggle between God and man. For if man were to wrest from God all that is His by rights, he must, in order to keep that control, somehow rid the society of God, so that the common man will believe that the temporal and human politic is the highest authority.

Modern Political Fantasy

Here lies the turning point. Political Philosophy and Non-fiction have done their work in bringing man’s attention to the motions governance takes. Political Fiction has made its debut and been accepted by those readers longing for more than mere hackneyed “frou-frou.” And having even conquered Political Science Fiction, having introduced it to a world normally skeptical of all that is fantastic, what use or precedent is there for Political Fantasy? If the purpose of Political Fantastic Fiction is to take a political situation in this world and extrapolate it; if Politics is often a power struggle between God’s rights and man’s pride-what benefit is there in placing the problems of this world into a completely different world? How would such a story work? How could it not be rejected as an impossibility?

Yet, several Political Fantasy novels exist and are commercially successful in today’s literature. All those fairy tales that touch upon the form of governance-often monarchical-point us to the classical and theological belief that a monarchy is the best form of governance. Tolkein’s *Lord of the Rings* is a literary map of how one king was restored to his throne. C. S. Lewis answers the question of God’s presence in any world outside of our own in his *Chronicles of Narnia*, where the ultimate ruler is Aslan-a metaphor for Christ. Novels such as L. Ron Hubbard’s *Dune* explore the intrigues of a technologically advanced court. Guy Gavriel Kay’s *Tigana* is the study of invasion, revolution and counterrevolution. Theresa Edgerton’s several books about the nation of Celydonn carefully reconstruct Medieval society, adding in the impossible element of “magic.”

These books, and so many others, begin to apply the possibilities that Emile Zola set out when he proposed “Scientific Fiction.” Cite. [sic] As exemplified in his novels such as *Germinal* and *L’assomoir*, Zola sets up Realistic Political situations, such as the oppression of coal miners in *Germinal*, places characters within that context, and then “lets them loose,” recording their actions as though an indifferent reporter. So, in *Germinal*, he does not shrink from showing the grime as well as the nobility, the heroics as well as its ultimate futility.

³³ Huxley, Aldous. *Brave New World*. New York: Bantam Books, (c) 1960. p. 8.

³⁴ *Ibid.* p. 159-160.

Paula Volsky's novel *Illusion* exemplifies Zola's criteria, setting up a world of Exalted and oppressed and tracing the lines that lead a society to revolt against its leaders and then against the usurpers. It follows the thread of aristocracy to tyranny to republic by following the Exalted Eliste vo Derrivale as she falls and rises with the society. Volsky adds in several interesting uses of power, such as the Purring to celebrate the seigneur's return in Chapter Two, and the Kokotte, a sort of sentient guillotine, during the book's equivalent of the Terror. Several examples of revolutionary literature are provided, ranging from the moderate Shorvi Nerienne calling for a reform ("the rule of a king and his Exalted is neither a law of Nature, nor yet a historical inevitability. Change is quite possible"³⁵) to the bloodthirsty unfounded cries of Whiss v'Aleur and his Reparationists ("You can get even with the demons, my friends.... You make them pay you back. With interest."³⁶). The beauty of Volsky's creation lies in her restrained use of magic and her interwoven use of technology. By blending the two, and adding in elements recognizable to the reader as variations on our own history, she makes the Fantasy more readily accessible to any reader, whether a fan of realistic or fantastic fiction.

Examples of Political Fantasy

But this can be taken one step farther. As was stated previously, Fantasy solely necessitates the creation of an entirely separate world from our own. Although magic or advanced technology are the easiest and most conventional means of achieving a differentiation between our world and the one described in a given book, neither is indispensable to Fantasy. Much of the actual differentiation will lie in the history and geography, and consequently in the customs, society, and, of course, politics. All of fiction is a study of the human soul. Fantasy is the laboratorial [sic] study of humans in situations tailored to a particular hypothetical question. The subsequent world created may then, on the surface, resemble our own at first. The exception will be in names, places, events, et cetera.

This returns us to the question of language that so consumed the giants of Political Science Fiction. Returning to the swiftly shrinking lexicon, and applying the rules of Political Fantasy, let us examine the short story "Last Words" as an example of Political Fantasy. A world is created: a seaport nation, Medina. Now, on this palate, set the political scheme: the Simplist Commonwealth where words have been stripped down to their basics, with no synonyms or antonyms, no "ambiguities and shades of meaning."³⁷ They do not have the words "beautiful," "wonderful," "gorgeous," "lovely;" they only have the paltry word "pretty." All their words are likewise starved. All mention of God has been purged from the common mind, for the absolute authority must lie with the Simplists. But "it [is] natural to feel there's a God,"³⁸ so a new word, Lucience ("light" = "enlightenment") is added as a state, not a deity to be desired. And the afterlife is a sort of Nirvana-esque "Simplicity," where all souls meld together, as opposed to Christ's promise of continued and perfected individuation, "In my Father's house are many rooms."³⁹ Adding in historical background, we learn that:

³⁵ Volsky, Paula. *Illusion*. New York: Bantam Books, (c) 1992. p. 19-20.

³⁶ *Ibid.* p. 156.

³⁷ Orwell, George. "1984." *The Orwell Reader*. New York: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich, Inc., (c) 1956. p. 412.

³⁸ Huxley, Aldous. *Brave New World*. New York: Bantam Books, (c) 1960. p. 159.

³⁹ Orchard, Dom Bernard, O.S.B., Reverent R.C. Fuller, D.D., L.S.S., editors. "John 14:2." *Ignatius Bible*. Imprimatur Bishop Peter W. Bartholome. United States of America: Ignatius Press, (c) 1966. p. 99.

“Two hundred and thirty-six years ago the Theosophic [“God-knowledge”] Wars ended...after five centuries or more of struggle. The Mayvndeists [“Beauty-deified”] lost, the Simplists won. Medina discarded her Monarchy for a Commonwealth. Her liberty for-Simplicity. She strives for Lucience, now; not for [God]. She withdrew from the world, closing her ports and borders to her sister nations. She allowed the sea to cut deeply into her land and created the Valez Ravine. She built Terralucien [“Earth-light”] with its mighty walls and mountaintops, its bleak plains and precise angles. She allowed her words to slip away. And now Medina lies both dumb and blind-without sensation, without thought, without the commerce of ideas and words-fetal.”⁴⁰

But the human spirit can not be put down; he will always explore the frontier, no matter how near or how distant. If words are censored, new words-the building blocks of new ideas-will still be coined. And in Medina, they are put on the black market, sold by Hawkers, coined by Dreamers.

Now, the story: a descendent of the Mayvndeist Empire, Solon, is no typical Dreamer, coining ridiculous words (“What was his latest monstrosity? Sjeklyg? Something having to do with preservatives, I think.”⁴¹) to earn a meal. He is searching for his “Something Other,” who is “the highest, of all existing things,”⁴² “something than which nothing greater can be thought”⁴³—God. In his search, he discovers the idea of the Supreme Being, and then the name. So when he is caught by the Watchmen, and is brought to execution, he is asked, jokingly, if he has any last words. Looking out to the assembled crowd, finding the narrator of the story to whom he has explained the idea, he says, “God.”

In Medina, there is no magic, no exceptional technology-nothing but the everyday aspects of our life rearranged to form a test world in which to show where our world is going. The subject matter is best set in another world so that the history can be tailored to create the sociopolitical scheme that will result in such a Commonwealth.

Defense: Wrap-Up

Like a funhouse mirror, like a shattered glass, fantasy has the ability to make the reader view himself and his world in a completely different light. The writer of fantasy makes the familiar unfamiliar. As the Romantic poets Wordsworth and Coleridge attempted in their *Lyrical Ballads*, and Wordsworth explained in his *Preface to Lyrical Ballads*,

The principal object then proposed in these poems was to choose incidents and situations from common life, and to relate or describe them, throughout, as far as was possible in a selection of language really used by men, and, at the same time, to throw over them a certain coloring of imagination, whereby ordinary things should be presented to the mind in an unusual aspect.⁴⁴

⁴⁰ Snyder, Emily. “Last Words.” (c) 1999. p. 9-10. [Lost Media]

⁴¹ Ibid. p. 17.

⁴² St. Anselm. “Monologion.” *A New, Interpretive Translation of St. Anselm's Monologion and Proslogion*. Trans. Jasper Hopkins. Minneapolis: The Arthur J. Banning Press, (c) 1986. p. 65.

⁴³ St. Anselm. “Proslogion.” *A New, Interpretive Translation of St. Anselm's Monologion and Proslogion*. Trans. Jasper Hopkins. Minneapolis: The Arthur J. Banning Press, (c) 1986. p. 225.

⁴⁴ Wordsworth, William. “Preface to Lyrical Ballads.” *Readings Honor VII* (Honor 401): Fall 1998. Ed. Dominic A. Aquila. Steubenville: Franciscan University of Steubenville, (c) 1998. p. 3-4.

The fantastic can only exist because of the realistic. Yet the world “discredits supernatural stories that have some foundation, simply by telling natural stories that have no foundation.”⁴⁵ Continuing this line, Lewis writes:

But you cannot go on “explaining away” forever: you will find that you have explained explanation itself away. You cannot go on “seeing through” things forever. The whole point of seeing through something is to see something through it.... If you see through everything, then everything is transparent. But a wholly transparent world is an invisible world. To “see through” all things is the same as not to see.⁴⁶

Many modern skeptical books do indeed “see through;” fantasy “looks into.” The fantastic exists because man sees the realistic for what it is, and sets that transcendental, pure view down on paper. Conventional figures in magical fantasy were created as an allegory to the inner workings of the soul: giants came from a sense of wonder, dragons from a sense of fear.

This is not to say that the genre is perfect, or that it is used perfectly at all times by all people, authors, publishers and readers alike. So many writers of Fantasy are often writing just to earn a dollar, to put pure emotional and fantastic junk on the page like a mythological cafeteria line. As Huxley and Bradbury warned, so many authors and publishers seek merely to provide a moment’s pleasure to the audience, with no concern for longevity, reason, or purpose. One can almost hear those vast hackneyed denizens speaking in concord with Bradbury’s Firechief:

You must understand that our civilization is so vast that we can’t have our minorities upset and stirred. Ask yourself, what do we want in this country, above all? People want to be happy, isn’t that right? Haven’t you heard it all your life? I want to be happy, people say. Well, aren’t they? Don’t we keep them moving, don’t we give them fun? That’s all we live for, isn’t it? For pleasure, for titillation? And you must admit our culture provides plenty of these.⁴⁷

Thus say the politics behind literature and all the arts today. But the arts always have been and always will be a counterbalance to the injustices and absurdities of the world. The arts have the power to lift the viewer upwards, towards the sublime, the heavens, and God. The arts, as much as any scalpel in a surgeon’s hand, can dissect those elements, so often melded together, that form our world. The arts can bring awareness, as much as they bring pleasure and happiness. The two are not necessarily mutually exclusive.

But in order to achieve this either in the arts, or in literature, or in fiction, or in Political Fantasy, the author must first be grounded in that which is true, good, just and beautiful—the author must be founded in God. Otherwise, all is for naught. Political Fantasy is the study of politics, that is the force-human or divine—that moves and shapes a society, in a fabricated world. Let us not forget the Divine.

⁴⁵ Chesterton, G. K. *Orthodoxy*. San Francisco: Ignatius Press, (c) 1908. p. 49.

⁴⁶ Lewis, C.S. *The Abolition of Man*. New York: Touchstone, (c) 1975. p. 86-87.

⁴⁷ Bradbury, Ray. *Fahrenheit 451*. New York: Ballantine Books, Inc., (c) 1953. p. 54.

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Glossary

- Alternate History** Fantastic Fiction wherein the history of this world is tampered with, (i.e., Napoleon never lived), and its results explicated and theorised by means of a story.
- Alternate Reality** A subgenre and hybrid of Urban Fantasy and Alternate History; this often fun and extraordinarily small genre not only alters this world's history, but also its dynamics. Since this sub-genre is small, it has not been swayed one way or another in terms of morals. However, with the advent of *The Shadow of Albion* it's leaning more towards secular paganism. (*Note*: It's not too late to reclaim it! Hint. Hint.)
- Classification** The third division of artwork into what general rules will be applied. In literature, the classifications for prose are Fiction and Non-Fiction.
- Cyberpunk** A subgenre of Science Fiction; this deals with the effect of the internet/virtual reality/cloning/etc. (i.e., plausible science fiction) within a Dark Science Fiction setting. Generally set in the near future, often with psychadellic effects, often dangerous morality. An example is the film *The Matrix*.
- Dark Fantasy** A subgenre of Fantasy (also Dark Science Fiction); this genre is almost always overrun by those who are not merely secular pagans, but tend more towards Satanism. Vampirism, bondage, sado-masochism, gore, etc. are common elements.
- Epic Fantasy** A subgenre of Fantasy; often cross-referenced with "High Fantasy." This sub-genre includes not only Tolkein and his Several Dwarves, but also those original classics, such as *Beowulf*, *Sir Gawain and the Green Knight*, and various other ancient epics.
- Fairy Tales** A subgenre of Fantasy; these include the Grimms, Andersons, Arabian Nights, Aesops, etc. of the world. Almost always excellent in both literary and moral quality. A recent surge has been made by secular paganism to subvert the children's tales which are predominantly Catholic in theme, in order to sway children early on in the neo-paganistic mores. Again, a major battlefield!
- Fantastic Fiction** Any fiction that takes place within the confines of another world, or in this world but with significant aberration within its history, future, physics or dynamics.
- Fantasy** The purest form of Fantastic Fiction: the majority of the action does not take place within this world.

Fiction	Prose based on something that did not happen or has not happened, implementing plot and character to exemplify thought.
Form	The first category when dividing the arts. Some forms are artwork, literature, music, drama, et cetera.
Genre	A style or type, in this case relating specifically to literature; e.g., science-fiction, mystery, romance, etc.
Hard Science Fiction	A subgenre of Science Fiction; almost strictly “nuts’n’bolts” literature, wherein the author pauses the plot to describe exactly how something works.
High Fantasy	A subgenre of Fantasy; occasionally known as “Epic Fantasy,” this generally deals with kings, quests, and a fair amount of Tolkeinesque literature. Magic is often a mysterious force, and there’s often an empire at stake. For “Low Fantasy” see “Sword and Sorcery.”
Humorous Fantasy	A subgenre of Fantasy; unsurprisingly, funny.
Humorous Science Fiction	A subgenre of Science Fiction; unsurprisingly, funny.
Literature	Books, magazines, articles, plays, short stories, poems—anything that utilizes the written word.
Militaristic Fantasy	A subgenre of Fantasy; a little-used subgenre, created mainly to answer the original Science Fiction subgenre. The emphasis is on militaristic tactics in a completely different world.
Militaristic Science Fiction	A subgenre of Science Fiction; this deals primarily with the question of war and science’s effect upon it. For an example, see <i>Ender’s Game</i> by Orson Scott Card.
Non-Fiction	Prose based on something that has happened or is happening.
Political Fantasy	A subgenre of Fantasy; differentiated from Political Science Fiction by its being in a completely different world (see above definitions of “Fantasy” vs. “Science Fiction”). The emphasis or study of this world, though, centers not merely on the social (i.e., human) interactions, but on the form of politics as it affects society.
Politics	The distribution of power within a society; the forces behind a society—human or divine.
Prose	The organization of the written word into paragraph form.

Realistic Fantasy	A subgenre of Fantasy; this subgenre is generally associated almost exclusively with Latin American Fantastic Fiction. Its hallmark is the use of the paranormal as if it were common in today's society. Differentiated from Urban Fantasy by its quality of literature (much better).
Realistic Fiction	Any fiction that takes place within the confines of this world with little to no aberration in its present history, physics or dynamics.
Science Fantasy	A subgenre and hybrid of Fantasy and Science Fiction; this, too, is a small sub-genre, fairly new and not fully developed. Its hallmarks are adding in elements of advanced technology into Fantasy works, as well as treating the fantastic with scientific explanation.
Science Fiction	Another form of Fantastic Fiction: the majority of the action takes place in this world and universe, usually speculating on the future, and involving technical advancements.
Speculative Fiction	Another name for the supergenre of Fantastic Fiction and/or the genre of Science Fiction.
Steampunk	A subgenre of Alternate History; this generally deals with advanced technology in the altered past.
Style	The category that subdivides forms into how that art is presented. In literature, the styles may be prose, poetry, plays and so on. In artwork, the styles may be painting, sculpture, et cetera.
Subgenre	A subdivision of a genre; e.g., high fantasy, dark fantasy, cyberpunk, space opera.
Supergenre	The larger class of genres; specifically in the Fiction Class: Realistic and Fantastic Fiction
Sword and Sorcery	A subgenre of Fantasy; arguably also known as "Low Fantasy," this stories often deal with hack-and-slash heroics, obligatory questing, and minimal worldbuilding. The emphasis is on the action rather than the thought. Common characters are witches and mercenaries. At the moment, the most fertile breeding ground for secular paganism, and the most common and preferred genre. (*Note*: The major publisher, at the moment of S&S;, is DAW books).
Traditional Fantasy	A subgenre of Fantasy; this style of literature can be seen in a variety of ways: stay-at-home High Fantasy, adult Fairy Tales, world-built Sword and Sorcery, and anything else that's middle of the road fantasy.

- Urban Fantasy** A subgenre of Fantasy; the action takes place in this world at this time, with no change in Earth's history, but rather in its dynamics (i.e., physics: usually magic is possible). Another area most often under the influence of secular paganism.
- World** What is described in Genesis 1-2, or, in literature, any variation on what God has done (with realization that all we "create" is due solely to what God has truly Created). A world includes all the history, physics, politics, society, universe and other dynamics that are found in this world/universe.
- Worldbuilding** The hallmark of Fantasy. Worldbuilding is the "creation" of a purely fictional world for purposes of a story to be played out in it. Geography, weather, history, society, religion, flora, fauna, etc. all must be dealt with and inserted in their place within the context of the story. For examples of excellent worldbuilders, see Tolkein, as well as the Worldbuilders page.

Hierarchy of the Arts

The following charts are not meant to be comprehensive, but to show the basic line from general to specific artistic titles.

- The first chart shows the titular relation any artform may take.
- The second follows the direct line from *Literature* to *Political Fantasy*.
- And the final chart shows a more complete diagram for all of literature.

It is my sincere hope to one day have something more like a comprehensive map, applicable to all the arts—any suggestions, esp. in specificities, are more than welcome!

Titular Chart

Literature Chart

Literature

|

Prose

|

Fiction

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Fantastic Fiction

|

Fantasy

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Political Fantasy

Branching Literature Chart

Branching Subgenre Chart

Archival Links

Political Fantasy Thesis

https://web.archive.org/web/20011118123140/http://members.tripod.com/Snyder_AMDG/Political1.html

https://web.archive.org/web/20011118123443/http://members.tripod.com/Snyder_AMDG/Political2.html

https://web.archive.org/web/20011118123704/http://members.tripod.com/Snyder_AMDG/Political3.html

Glossary

https://web.archive.org/web/20011118193850/http://members.tripod.com/Snyder_AMDG/Glossary.html

Bibliography

https://web.archive.org/web/20011118123820/http://members.tripod.com/Snyder_AMDG/Bibliography.html

Charts

https://web.archive.org/web/20011118124022/http://members.tripod.com/Snyder_AMDG/Hierarchy.html